

Green Logistics Practices and Operational Excellence of Oil and Gas Servicing Companies in South-South, Nigeria

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The study examined the correlation between green logistics techniques, namely reverse logistics and green packaging, and operational excellence, as evaluated by operational efficiency, among oil and gas servicing firms in South-South, Nigeria. This study was based on the theoretical framework of industrial ecology theory. The positivist-based study used cross-sectional survey research. Standardized questionnaire with five-point Likert scales was deployed for data collection. 1,038 middle and upper level managers from 153 oil and gas companies in state capitals were targeted. These firms are registered with Nigerian Midstream and Downstream Petroleum Regulatory Authority. A 281-person sample was calculated using Krejcie and Morgan's method. Simple random sampling was adopted using random numbers. With a 0.05 significance criterion, Partial Least Squares-Structural Equation Modelling was deployed to test the hypotheses. The study found that while reverse logistics strategies may not directly affect operational efficiency, green packaging initiatives may improve operational excellence in South-South Nigerian oil and gas servicing firms. It was recommended that Management of oil and gas servicing organizations should improve reverse logistics adoption, by offering incentives to return packaging materials and returning abandoned packaging and items to suppliers for recycling or reuse helps achieve this. Also, Managers of oil and gas servicing organizations should emphasize green packaging projects, by employing recyclable materials and improving package designs.

Key words: Green logistics practices, operational excellence, operational efficiency.

INTRODUCTION

The oil sector has a substantial role in Nigeria's economy, representing around 29.1% of its Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (Oladimeji, 2022). Although the Nigerian oil sector has made beneficial contributions, it also has substantial obstacles such as expensive and delayed projects, a high number of fatalities, unpredictable oil prices, outdated rules and regulations, corruption, and frequent oil spills (Rui, 2018). Overall, these problems

have a significant impact on the operational efficiency of these companies. The significance of operational excellence in oil and gas servicing organisations cannot be overstated. Operational excellence has the potential to boost productivity, mitigate health and safety concerns, enhance environmental performance, and augment operational efficiency (Muazu, 2020).

The topic addressed in this study is the insufficient degree of operational excellence exhibited by oil and gas servicing firms in the South-South region of Nigeria. Poor operational excellence is evident via deteriorating health, safety, and environmental (HSE) performance (Muazu,

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Hassan & Muazu, 2019), excessive bureaucracy and absence of creative strategies (Muhammad et al., 2022), and significant cost and time overruns (Rui, 2018). These problems can lead to higher expenses, reduced efficiency, compromised safety, and impeded innovation. Poor operational excellence in oil and gas industries has several negative consequences, such as decreased customer satisfaction, inefficiencies in project delivery, increased incidents and fatalities, oil spillage, gas flaring, and a lack of sustainable outcomes (Muhammad, Mehboob & Khurshid, 2016; Muazu, 2019; Mahmoud et al., 2023). Moreover, experts have contended that the factors contributing to a subpar degree of operational excellence encompass: insufficient funding, inadequate incentives for investors, a deficiently connected transportation system, inadequate equipment, as well as a dearth of managerial skills, knowledge, and experience (Ekpo, 2012).

In addition, the proposed remedies for addressing the issue of inadequate operational excellence encompass various elements, such as employee engagement, training, managerial dedication, resource accessibility, leadership, project prioritisation, organisational culture, communication, customer and supplier relationships, performance management, and teamwork (Ruben & Fontes, 2016). Nevertheless, despite the proposed remedies, the issue of inadequate operational excellence continues to endure, particularly within the oil and gas servicing sector. This indicates a void in the existing literature within this specific context. Hence, this study aims to address the existing knowledge vacuum by conducting a thorough analysis of green logistics practices and their links to the operational excellence of oil and gas servicing companies in the South-South region of Nigeria. The study aims to achieve the following particular objectives:

- (i). Assess the relationship between reverse logistics and operational excellence of oil and gas firms servicing firms in South South, Nigeria.
- (ii). Investigate the relationship between green packaging and operational excellence of oil and gas firms servicing firms in South South, Nigeria.

The research questions are as follows

- (iii). How does reverse logistics relates with operational excellence of oil and gas servicing firms in South South, Nigeria?
- ii. What is the link between green packaging and operational excellence of oil and gas servicing firms in South South, Nigeria?

The research hypotheses are

HO1: Reverse logistics does not significantly relate with operational excellence of oil and gas servicing firms in

South South, Nigeria.

HO2: There is no significant nexus between green packaging and operational excellence of oil and gas servicing firms in South South, Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Green Logistics Practices: Green logistics solutions pertain to the ecologically conscious transportation of commodities from the point of origin to the point of consumption (Hampus & Henrik, 2014). The technique entails the synchronisation of logistical processes in order to minimise their ecological footprint (Ismail et al., 2019). According to Weng and Chen (2015), green logistics practices refer to the implementation of environmentally-friendly techniques in several aspects of logistics, including transportation, packaging, storage, route optimisation, fuel efficiency, and reverse logistics.

Reverse Logistics: Reverse Logistics (RL) refers to the efficient handling of materials that are returned by consumers. This includes activities such as restoring, reengineering, recycling, liquidating, or disposing of garbage in a manner that is ecologically sustainable. Fleischmann (2000) links reverse logistics to secondary commodities, which encompass items that are rejected, denied, or returned following the initial sale.

Green Packaging: Green packaging only use environmentally-friendly materials for packaging, with a focus on ensuring that products are both efficient and non-hazardous to human health and the environment (Vendosel et al., 2021). Green packaging, as defined by Hazen and Hanna (2011), encompasses any modifications made by product manufacturers or service providers to reduce the environmental effect of packaging materials and procedures throughout the distribution of products and services to consumers.

Operational Excellence: Operational excellence encompasses the attainment of the utmost quality and performance in all aspect of a business's operations. Operational excellence, as defined by Hammer (2004), is the attainment of superior performance via the optimisation of existing operational methods. This involves ensuring that work is carried out in the correct manner, with the aim of minimising errors, expenses, and delays, while maintaining the core approach to doing the task.

Operational Efficiency: Operational efficiency is the quantitative relationship between the outputs obtained from a firm and the input required to carry out a commercial function. Efficiency, as defined by Agarwal (2013), refers to the capacity to use the least amount of resources necessary in order to generate an output or accomplish a desired outcome. Efficiency refers to the process of achieving the highest possible output or outcomes with the fewest resources, such as labour, effort, time, or cash.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Industrial Ecology Theory, (1989).

This inquiry was based on the theoretical review of industrial ecology theory, which was initially developed by Frosch and Gallopoulos in 1989. The idea revolves around the strategic coordination and administration of production, logistics, and consumption systems to facilitate their interaction with the natural environment. This aims to create a balanced and eco-friendly ecosystem that provides individuals with a sustainable lifestyle. This notion may be applied to justify the necessity of implementing environmentally-conscious logistical practices in oil and gas service organisations to meet customer demands in a sustainable manner.

Empirical Reviews

Kericho, Kenya, Chemutai and Mbeche (2018), examined how reverse logistics affects multinational tea processing businesses' operations. Descriptive survey research was used to survey 62 officers from Uniliver Tea, James Finlay, and Williamson Tea Kenya Limited in Kericho County. The researchers collected data using closed-ended questionnaires and did descriptive statistical analysis using frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations. Multiple regression and ANOVA were used to examine how reverse logistics affects multinational tea processing enterprises in Kenya. The results showed that reverse logistics significantly affected business performance.

Sambu (2016), explored how eco-friendly packaging affects Nairobi County industrial enterprises' operations. The study used institutional and resource-based theories. We used an explanatory research design. A survey examined 133 CEOs from 47 Nairobi County businesses. The structured questionnaire's internal reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha. In descriptive statistics, means and standard deviations were used. Data was also examined using multiple regression models. The results showed that eco-friendly packaging is crucial to Kenyan industrial success.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a cross-sectional survey research design as there and a structured questionnaire based on a Likert's five-point scale was utilized. The target population was 153 oil servicing companies in South South Nigeria, which are registered with Nigerian Midstream and Downstream Petroleum Regulatory Authority, and located in the state capitals and the elements of the accessible population were 1,038 middle and top-level managers of the registered oil servicing companies. The Krejcie and Morgan's formula was

utilized to determine a sample size of 281 respondents, and the simple random sampling was adopted with the aid of random numbers. Partial least squares-structural equation modeling was deployed to test the hypotheses at 0.05 significance level via SmartPLS 4.1.0.0. 281 copies of the questionnaire were distributed, but only 225 were retrieved, indicating a retrieval rate of 80.07%. Out of retrieved copies, 23 (8.19%) were discarded due to missing replies. Overall, 202 copies (71.89%) were found to be adequately completed and usable. Cronbach's Alpha coefficient value of 0.7 was used as reliability threshold. Convergent validity is considered sufficient when the average variance extracted (AVE) is 0.5 or above. Discriminant validity is established when the square root of a construct's AVE is larger than its correlation with all other constructs (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). In statistical analysis, t-values more than 1.96 and p-values less than 0.05 are considered to be statistically significant. On the other hand, R²-values of 0.75, 0.50, and 0.25 indicate large, moderate, or modest levels of predictive accuracy, respectively. (Hair et al., 2014).

Figure 2, figure 3 and table 1 reveals the reflective measurement model of green logistics practices (reverse logistics and green packaging) and operational efficiency (operational efficiency) of oil and gas companies in South-South, Nigeria, with the following interpretation: The reflective measurement model reveals strong reliability and validity across all constructs. Specifically, the average path coefficient (β) for REVERSE LOGISTICS is 0.756, indicating a strong relationship between the latent construct and its indicators. Indicator Reliability (I_k^2) values range from 0.410 to 0.667, all surpassing the threshold of 0.50 recommended by Hulland (1999), demonstrating satisfactory reliability. The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is 0.526, meeting the criteria for convergent validity, and Composite Reliability (ρ_c) is 0.898, exceeding the minimum threshold of 0.7 for reliability as suggested by Nunnally & Bernstein (1994). Additionally, the Effect sizes (f^2) range from 0.162 to 0.193, indicating small to medium effects of the exogenous latent variable. Predictive Accuracy (R²) is 0.881, suggesting a substantial level of predictive accuracy according to Hair et al. (2014), and Cronbach's Alpha (α) is 0.881, indicating good internal consistency reliability.

Similarly, for GREEN PACKAGING, the average path coefficient (β) is 0.798, indicating a strong relationship between the latent construct and its indicators. Indicator Reliability (I_k^2) values range from 0.377 to 0.738, all exceeding the threshold of 0.50, demonstrating satisfactory reliability. The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is 0.625, meeting the criteria for convergent validity, and Composite Reliability (ρ_c) is 0.920, exceeding the minimum threshold of 0.7 for reliability. The Effect sizes (f^2) range from 0.109 to 0.122, indicating small effects of the exogenous latent variable. Predictive Accuracy (R²) is 0.911, suggesting a substantial level of

predictive accuracy, and Cronbach's Alpha (α) is 0.911, indicating good internal consistency reliability. Furthermore, for OPERATIONAL EFFICIENCY, the average path coefficient (β) is 0.780, indicating a strong relationship between the latent construct and its indicators. Indicator Reliability (Ik2) values range from 0.417 to 0.778, all exceeding the threshold of 0.50, demonstrating satisfactory reliability. The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is 0.619, meeting the criteria for convergent validity, and Composite Reliability (ρ_c) is 0.865, exceeding the minimum threshold of 0.7 for reliability. The Effect sizes (f^2) range from 0.127 to 0.145, indicating small effects of the exogenous latent variable. Predictive Accuracy (R^2) is 0.835, suggesting a substantial level of predictive accuracy, and Cronbach's Alpha (α) is 0.835, indicating good internal consistency reliability. Overall, the reflective measurement model demonstrates strong reliability and validity for all constructs, with substantial predictive accuracy and satisfactory internal consistency reliability across the board.

In table 2 of the discriminant validity analysis, the numbers on the diagonal indicate the square roots of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for each construct. The values off the diagonal show the correlations between pairs of constructs. The square root of the AVE for Green Logistics Practices is 1.000, which means it accounts for 100% of its own variance. The correlation coefficient between Green Logistics Practices and Green Purchasing is 0.397, between Green Logistics Practices and Operational Efficiency is 0.267, and between Green Logistics Practices and Reverse Logistics is 0.328. The square root of the average value of effectiveness (AVE) for Green Purchasing is 0.643.

The correlation coefficient between Green Purchasing and Green Logistics Practices is 0.397, whereas the correlation coefficient between Green Purchasing and Operational Efficiency is 0.686. The square root of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for Operational Efficiency is 0.816. The correlation coefficients between Operational Efficiency and Green Logistics Practices, Green Purchasing, and Reverse Logistics are 0.267, 0.686, and 0.665, respectively. The square root of the average variance extracted (AVE) for reverse logistics is 0.742. The correlation coefficients between Reverse Logistics and Green Logistics Practices, Reverse Logistics and Green Purchasing, and Reverse Logistics and Operational Efficiency are 0.328, 0.881, and 0.665, respectively.

Discriminant validity is established by comparing the square root of each construct's average variance extracted (AVE) with the correlations between that construct and other constructs. If the square root of the AVE is higher than the correlations, then indicates that the construct is distinct from the others. This suggests that each construct exhibits a greater degree of similarity with its own indicators compared to indicators of other

constructs, hence proving the distinctiveness of the constructs.

DISCUSSIONS OF FINDINGS

i. Relationship between Reverse Logistics and Operational Efficiency: From figures 4 and 5, and table 2, the results of the hypothesis HO1 testing suggest that there is no significant relationship between Reverse Logistics and Operational Efficiency, with a path coefficient (β value) of 0.270, a p-value of 0.084, and a t-value of 1.730. While the path coefficient falls within the range considered a weak to moderate correlation according to Cohen (1988), the p-value exceeds the significance threshold of 0.05, indicating non-significance. Additionally, the t-value is below the critical value of 1.96, further supporting non-significance. However, the R^2 value (coefficient of determination) of 0.456 indicates a moderate level of predictive accuracy, suggesting that Reverse Logistics explains approximately 45.6% of the variance in Operational Efficiency. Surprisingly, this finding disagrees with the earlier study by Chemutai and Mbeche (2018) who found a significant influence of reverse logistics on organizational performance of multinational tea processing companies in Kenya.

ii. Relationship between Green Packaging and Operational Efficiency: From figures 4 and 5, and table 2, the results of the hypothesis HO2 testing suggest that there is a significant relationship between Green Packaging and Operational Efficiency. The path coefficient (β value) of 0.447 exceeds the threshold for a moderate correlation according to Cohen (1988). Additionally, the p-value of 0.007 is below the significance level of 0.05, indicating statistical significance. Furthermore, the t-value of 2.697 exceeds the critical value of 1.96, further supporting significance. The R^2 value (coefficient of determination) of 0.468 indicates a moderate level of predictive accuracy, suggesting that Green Packaging and Operational Efficiency together explain approximately 46.8% of the variance in Operational Efficiency. This implies that implementing green packaging initiatives can positively impact operational excellence within this industry sector, potentially leading to cost savings, improved resource utilization, and environmental sustainability. Interestingly, this finding agrees with Sambu (2016) who found that green packaging is key determinants of business performance in the manufacturing in Kenya.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, while reverse logistics practices may not directly contribute to operational efficiency, adopting green packaging initiatives appears to be beneficial for enhancing Operational excellence within oil and gas

servicing companies in the South-South region of Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. Reverse Logistics and Operational Efficiency: Oil and gas servicing companies should enhance the implementation of reverse logistics practices to directly enhance operational efficiency. This can be achieved by providing special incentives to encourage the return of packaging materials and the recycling or reuse of used packaging and products to suppliers.
- ii. Green Packaging and Operational Efficiency: Given the significant relationship between Green Packaging and Operational Efficiency, it is strongly recommended that managers of oil and gas servicing companies should prioritize the adoption of green packaging initiatives. Implementing environmentally friendly packaging practices, such as using recyclable materials and optimizing packaging designs, can contribute to improving operational efficiency within these companies.

Suggestions for Further Research:

Further studies might investigate the possible moderating influences of contextual elements, such as organizational culture, industry legislation, and stakeholder perceptions. This could offer more profound understanding of the connection between green logistics practices and operational excellence. Moreover, expanding the research to various geographic areas or industrial sectors might facilitate the generalization of the results and uncover possible variances in the correlation between green logistics methods and operational efficiency.

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